

Impact of Rajyoga Meditation on Self-Esteem Among High School Students

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Abstract

Self-esteem is a crucial psychological factor that influences students' academic achievement, emotional well-being, social adjustment, and personality development. High school students often experience low self-esteem due to academic pressure, social comparison, emotional stress and excessive use of technology and social media. Poor self-esteem can negatively affect confidence, motivation, classroom participation and mental health.

Rajyoga Meditation, popularized by the Brahma Kumaris World Spiritual University, is an ancient meditation practice founded on spiritual awareness, constructive thought, and emotional balance. This narrative review examines the impact of Rajyoga Meditation on self-esteem among high school students through a review of literature related to meditation, mindfulness, adolescent mental health and personality development.

The reviewed studies indicate that meditation practices improve self-confidence, emotional regulation, self-awareness and psychological well-being. Rajyoga Meditation may help students develop positive thinking, emotional stability, self-discipline, and a healthy self-